

One Generalization of the Dicke-Type Models

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We discuss one family of possible generalizations of the Jaynes–Cummings and the Tavis–Cummings models using the technique of algebraic Bethe ansatz related to the Gaudin-type models. In particular, we present a family of (generically) non-Hermitian Hamiltonians that generalize paradigmatic quantum optical problems. New directions of our research may include studying physical properties of the obtained generalized models.

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1. Introduction

The Jaynes–Cummings model [1] plays the central role in the field of quantum optics, see, e.g., Refs. [2–5]. It describes an interaction between a single bosonic mode (e.g., a cavity photon of a fixed frequency ω) and a single two-level system (e.g., a qubit) with an energy gap Δ as follows:

$$H_{JC} = \omega a^\dagger a + \Delta \sigma^z + g(a\sigma^+ + a^\dagger\sigma^-). \quad (1.1)$$

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Here a^\dagger and a are bosonic creation and annihilation operators, respectively, and the Pauli sigma matrices $\sigma^{\pm,z}$ encode two-level qubit degree of freedom. The photon-qubit coupling strength g is assumed to be small. Note that in deriving the Hamiltonian (1.1) we neglect the so-called counter-rotating terms $a^\dagger\sigma^+$ and $a\sigma^-$, which are indeed present at the microscopic level.

A multi-qubit generalization of the model (1.1) is known as the Tavis–Cummings model [6] (or a limiting version of the celebrated Dicke model [7]; notable results on its studies have been obtained by Yudson [8, 9] by developing the contour representation) and describes an ensemble of two-level systems located in a region of space, which is smaller than a wavelength of a single bosonic mode

$$H_{TC} = \omega a^\dagger a + 2\Delta S^z + g(a^\dagger S^+ + a^\dagger S^-), \quad (1.2)$$

where $S^{\pm,z} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i^{\pm,z}$ is a collective spin describing an ensemble of two-level systems

placed in a region of space much smaller than the wavelength $\sim \omega^{-1}$ of bosonic mode. An exact stationary solution for the density matrix of the above model coupled to dissipative bath is shown to undergo a *nonequilibrium* first-order phase transition when the parameters of the frequency detuning or of the exciting-radiation power are changed, see Refs. [10] and [11] for more details and earlier references. We also note a recent interest in the Jaynes–Cummings and Tavis–Cummings models in the context of quantum technologies [12–14]. In particular, these and related models have been simulated using superconducting qubits [15–17].

Although both the Jaynes–Cummings and the Tavis–Cummings models have been well-studied in various regimes, their generalizations may have non-trivial properties, which can be studied with the use of a powerful method of the algebraic Bethe ansatz. Motivated by this idea, in this work we present a family of possible generalizations of the aforementioned models, which may lead to non-Hermitian Hamiltonians. We investigate their basic properties and discuss certain directions for further studies.

2. Integrability of Gaudin-type models

Models like (1.2) belong to the class of the so-called Gaudin-type integrable models. The central object behind integrability in these models is the existence of the so-called classical r -matrix that satisfies a classical version of the celebrated Yang–Baxter equation [18, 19]

$$[r_{12}, r_{13}] + [r_{12}, r_{23}] + [r_{13}, r_{23}] = 0, \quad (2.1)$$

where the r -matrix is defined in the tensor product of three Hilbert spaces, and one has the following notations: $r_{12} \equiv \sum_n a_n \otimes b_n \otimes 1$, $r_{23} = \sum_n 1 \otimes a_n \otimes b_n$, $r_{13} = \sum_n a_n \otimes 1 \otimes b_n$. Here a_n, b_n are the operators acting on these Hilbert spaces. The key identity responsible for the integrability

of a model reads as follows:

$$[L(\lambda) \otimes 1, 1 \otimes L(\mu)] + [r(\lambda - \mu), L(\lambda) \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes L(\mu)] = 0, \quad (2.2)$$

where the Lax matrix *in our context* is defined as a matrix with the operator-valued entries

$$L(\lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} A(\lambda) & B(\lambda) \\ C(\lambda) & -A(\lambda) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.3)$$

Here $A(\lambda)$, $B(\lambda)$, and $C(\lambda)$ are operators acting on the tensor product of bosonic and qubit degrees of freedom. The size of the L -matrix (2×2 in our case) defines the size of what is called the auxiliary space, which could be of arbitrary size. The relation (2.2) is an analogue of the Poisson brackets. Their associativity is guaranteed by the classical Yang–Baxter equation (2.1).

Let us now take the r -matrix of the rational form $r_{ab}(\lambda) = P_{ab}/\lambda$, where P_{ab} is a permutation operator acting between spaces a and b . In the matrix form P_{ab} is represented by the following 4×4 matrix:

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.4)$$

Then, substituting the L -matrix (2.3) into (2.2) and using the rational r -matrix specified above, we find that the operators A , B , and C satisfy the commutation relations of the $sl(2)$ loop algebra

$$[B(\lambda), C(\mu)] = 2 \frac{A(\lambda) - A(\mu)}{\lambda - \mu}, \quad (2.5)$$

$$[A(\lambda), B(\mu)] = \frac{B(\lambda) - B(\mu)}{\lambda - \mu}, \quad (2.6)$$

$$[A(\lambda), C(\mu)] = -\frac{C(\lambda) - C(\mu)}{\lambda - \mu}, \quad (2.7)$$

and

$$[A(\lambda), A(\mu)] = [B(\lambda), B(\mu)] = [C(\lambda), C(\mu)] = 0. \quad (2.8)$$

The following quantity

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{Tr}(L^2(\lambda)) = A^2(\lambda) + \frac{1}{2}(B(\lambda)C(\lambda) + C(\lambda)B(\lambda)) \quad (2.9)$$

has a key commutativity property:

$$[\text{Tr}(L^2(\lambda)), \text{Tr}(L^2(\mu))] = 0. \quad (2.10)$$

This quantity is a *generating* function for commuting Hamiltonians.

At this point, we have to specify a *representation* of the algebra in Eqs. (2.5)–(2.8). The Tavis–Cummings model (1.2) is obtained if the following identification is made

$$A(\lambda) = \frac{2\lambda}{g^2} - \frac{\omega}{g^2} + \frac{S^z}{\lambda - \Delta}, \quad (2.11)$$

$$B(\lambda) = \frac{2a}{g} + \frac{S^-}{\lambda - \Delta}, \quad (2.12)$$

$$C(\lambda) = \frac{2a^\dagger}{g} + \frac{S^+}{\lambda - \Delta}. \quad (2.13)$$

In this case [20] we arrive to the following expression:

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{Tr}(L^2(\lambda)) = \frac{1}{g^4}(2\lambda - \omega)^2 + \frac{4}{g^2}H_N + \frac{2}{g^2(\lambda - \Delta)}H_{TC} + \text{const}, \quad (2.14)$$

where $H_N = a^\dagger a + S^z$ is a total number of excitation which commutes with H_{TC} . Let us now proceed with looking for more general representations.

3. Generalization

One possible way of generalizing the above results is to search for a new representation of the Gaudin algebra (2.5)–(2.8). We found a faithful representation of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} A(\lambda) &= \left(\frac{1}{2}(\alpha_1\alpha_2 - \beta_1\beta_2)\lambda + \rho \right) I + \frac{S^z}{\lambda}, \\ B(\lambda) &= \alpha_1 a + \beta_1 a^\dagger + \gamma \frac{S^-}{\lambda}, \\ C(\lambda) &= \beta_2 a + \alpha_2 a^\dagger + \frac{S^+}{\gamma\lambda}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

with no restrictions on the complex-valued parameters $\alpha_{1,2}, \beta_{1,2}, \rho, \gamma$. In the above representation I is the identity operator. Then, for the generating function we obtain

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{Tr}(L^2(\lambda)) = H_0 + \frac{1}{\lambda}H_1 + \frac{1}{\lambda^2}C_2 + \frac{1}{4}\lambda^2(\alpha_1\alpha_2 - \beta_1\beta_2)^2 + \rho\lambda(\alpha_1\alpha_2 - \beta_1\beta_2), \quad (3.2)$$

where $C_2 = (S^z)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(S^+S^- + S^-S^+)$ is the second Casimir invariant of $SU(2)$ and we denoted

$$H_0 = \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_1\alpha_2 + \beta_1\beta_2 + 2\rho^2) + (\alpha_1\alpha_2 + \beta_1\beta_2)a^\dagger a + \alpha_2\beta_1(a^\dagger)^2 + \alpha_1\beta_2a^2 + (\alpha_1\alpha_2 - \beta_1\beta_2)S^z, \quad (3.3)$$

$$H_1 = \alpha_2\gamma a^\dagger S^- + \frac{\beta_1}{\gamma}a^\dagger S^+ + \frac{\alpha_1}{\gamma}a S^+ + \beta_2\gamma a S^- + 2\rho S^z. \quad (3.4)$$

Note that in Eq. (3.2), which is the Laurent-type expansion in terms of complex parameters

λ , all (operator-valued) coefficients commute. As a consequence, the physical Hamiltonian can be

constructed as an arbitrary linear combination of the coefficients in front of λ^k , for $k = 0, -1, -2$. Namely, $H_{\text{phys}} = H_0 + \kappa H_1$, with some κ . Also note that the coefficients in front of λ, λ^2 in Eq.(3.2) are proportional to the identity operator, and the same holds for the first term in Eq.(3.3).

4. Conclusions

In this short note, we have constructed a family of (generically) non-Hermitian Hamiltonians generalizing famous quantum optical problems. These Hamiltonians contain terms quadratic in bosonic operators and counter-rotating terms in boson-qubit coupling terms. In the future we plan to investigate their physical properties in more detail.

Using the known Bethe ansatz techniques, namely the separation of variables (see Refs. [20–22]), we plan to further investigate the physical properties of the novel family of models. Of particular interest is the possible existence of phase transitions. One more interesting direction could be related to a possible $gl(2, \mathbf{C})$ structure hidden in this model. This observation is coming from the obvious $gl(2)$ type structure in the bosonic sector of Eq. (3.1). Indeed, it can be made transparent by defining a transformation

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{a} \\ \tilde{a}^\dagger \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 & \alpha_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a \\ a^\dagger \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.1)$$

with the determinant $\alpha_1\alpha_2 - \beta_1\beta_2$, which systematically appears in Eq. (3.2). It could also be very interesting to study a dissipative version of the above model following the lines of Refs. [10, 11]. One more possible way of generalizing our findings is by including inhomogeneities, thus extending the results for the traditional Dicke model [20].

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